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Nasarawa State University Journal of Special and Inclusive Education (NSUJSIE)

ISSN: 3121-729X

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PRACTICAL TRAINING STRATEGIES ON ORIENTATION AND MOBILITY PERSONS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT

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Citation: Balla, H. J. & Jonathan, T. J. (2026). Practical Training Strategies on Orientation and Mobility Persons with Visual Impairment. *Nas. State Uni. J. of Spe. & Inclusive Edu*; 1(1), 130–139.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19413079>

Academic Editor: Dr. Jummai Jerry

Received: 14 November, 2025

Revised: 8 December, 2025

Accepted: 3 February, 2026

Published: 1 April, 2026

Abstract: *Orientation and mobility (O & M) are more than just technical skills; they are the fundamental building blocks of independence for people with visual impairments. These skills involve the ability to perceive, interpret, and navigate environments safely and efficiently using available sensory information. For persons with visual impairment, exploring their surroundings can be both challenging and motivating, depending on the level of training and sensory development. Effective O & M training enhances spatial awareness, hazard detection, and goal-oriented movement, thereby fostering autonomy and confidence. This paper explores the practical training strategies on orientation and mobility for persons with visual impairment, emphasizing the importance of perceptual development, visual, auditory, and tactile in acquiring and refining these skills. It highlights the role of sensory perception in facilitating safe, independent travel and discusses strategies to optimize perceptual abilities for better mobility outcomes.*

Keywords: Perception, persons with visual impairment, orientation and mobility

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Introduction

Movement forms a fundamental basis for learning. As children actively explore their environment and interact physically with it, meaningful learning occurs. However, individuals with visual impairments often require deliberate encouragement and support to explore their surroundings. For them, the environment may appear unfamiliar, unpredictable, or insufficiently stimulating, which can limit spontaneous exploration (Carolina, 2013).

Orientation is a core skill that enables individuals to understand where they are and how they relate to their environment. It involves environmental cues; such as sounds, tactile landmarks, and any available residual vision to develop a mental representation of space. According to Hill and Blasch (2000), orientation refers to the ability to determine one's position and direction within the environment through the effective use of all available senses. This capacity allows persons with visual impairments to recognize their location and plan purposeful movement with greater confidence and safety.

Hill and Blasch (2000) describe mobility as the capacity to move safely, efficiently, and effectively from one place to another. This includes practical abilities such as walking without tripping or falling, crossing streets safely, and using public transportation. These skills do not develop automatically; rather, they are acquired through carefully planned and systematic activities designed and implemented by orientation and mobility specialists. Such structured programmes support individuals in developing or relearning the concepts and techniques necessary for safe and independent travel within the home and the wider community (Fazzi & Naimy, 2010).

Mobility involves purposeful and safe physical movement through space and incorporates a range of functional skills, including walking, negotiating stairs, crossing roads, and using various modes of transportation. Beyond movement, mobility also requires the ability to detect obstacles, avoid hazards, and adjust to changing environmental conditions. Fazzi and Naimy (2010) emphasize that these competencies are developed through formal mobility instruction, where specialists teach strategies such as cane skills, route planning, and environmental awareness to promote independent travel.

In broader terms, mobility can be understood as physical movement combined with the effective negotiation of obstacles and hazards in the environment. The ultimate goal of mobility training is to ensure freedom of movement without injury, enhance safety during travel, and reduce the stress associated with navigation for individuals with visual impairments. While Braille supports intellectual independence, a well-developed sense of mobility enables functional independence by allowing individuals to recognize potential dangers and take appropriate evasive action during travel (Hill & Blasch, 2000).

Gargiulo (2006) further defines mobility as total physical movement involving a change in spatial location achieved under one's own power, typically in an upright position. Mobility ranges from movement within a single room to travel across towns, regions, or even countries. To be mobile, an individual must be able to gather, interpret, and use environmental information effectively in order to avoid hazards and reach destinations safely. For persons with visual impairments, this may involve the use of mobility aids such as a long cane, guide cane, or other supportive tools, as well as assistance from a human guide or escort when necessary.

Orientation and mobility refer to purposeful, goal-directed movement that involves knowing one's current location, understanding where one has come from, and determining where one intends

to go. In this sense, orientation and mobility are processes through which individuals use their senses to establish their position in relation to significant objects and features within the environment. As specialized professional fields within the area of blindness and low vision, orientation and mobility focus on teaching people of all ages how to travel safely, efficiently, and effectively. Orientation in particular, involves the ability to identify one's location and intended destination, whether navigating between rooms in a house or traveling independently within the community (Gargiulo, 2006).

Perceptual Development

Perception has been described by Emerson and Hatlen (1992) as a set of processes through which individuals acquire information from the stimulus energy present in their environment. Perception involves obtaining first-hand knowledge of the immediate surroundings through the use and integration of functional sensory receptors. For this information to be effectively gathered, an individual must be aware of environmental events and demonstrate the ability to selectively and discriminatively respond to relevant sensory input using the available senses.

Foulke (1987) emphasized the importance of comparing perceptual systems based on the type, quantity, and quality of information they provide, noting that different senses respond to varying forms and ranges of stimulus energy. Vision is often described as the "queen of the senses" because of the breadth and richness of information it typically supplies compared to other sensory systems. Perception begins with the active search for relevant stimuli in the environment, during which the sense organs are positioned to receive specific forms of stimulus energy. This search process is regulated by the central nervous system, which draws on stored information from past experiences to guide attention, select targets, and coordinate the muscular responses involved in seeking behavior (Emerson & Hatlen, 1992; Foulke, 1987). Consequently, previously learned concepts play a critical role in shaping perception, as they support memory, interpretation, and the understanding of new experiences introduced to the learner.

Visual Perception

Human beings are widely regarded as highly vision-oriented, with a substantial proportion of learning occurring through visual input. Telford and Sawrey (1977) estimated that approximately 85 percent of typical classroom experiences are visual in nature. Emerson and Hatlen (1992) noted that visual perception is largely concerned with spatial systems, involving the analysis of spatial patterns and the acquisition of spatially distributed information. Through vision, individuals obtain information about the extent of space, the location and movement of objects, as well as their shapes, textures, and colours. These visual-spatial processes form an essential foundation for the development of orientation and mobility skills. Supporting this view, Gibson (1987) argued that spatial knowledge represents one of the most fundamental forms of human knowledge, and that limitations in interpreting spatial information stemming from an inadequate conception of space can lead to far-reaching developmental consequences.

Emerson and Hatlen (1992) further highlighted the advantages of vision in learning and development. Vision allows individuals to gather sensory information from a distance, perceive objects as unified wholes, and process sensory input rapidly. The luminous energy received through visual receptors provides rich spatial information critical for perceptual and cognitive development. In contrast, persons with visual impairments do not have the same access to this continuous and abundant visual stimulation that sighted peers experience, which places them at a disadvantage in acquiring incidental spatial and environmental information.

As a result, individuals with visual impairments often experience reduced stimulation that lacks the richness and motivational value of visual input (Gibson, 1987). Vision plays a key role in motivating environmental exploration during infancy and early childhood. While sighted children are naturally drawn to their surroundings and engage in direct sensory exploration, the environment may not offer the same level of attraction or motivation for children with visual impairments. Consequently, they may have fewer incidental learning opportunities. Orientation and mobility instruction can help bridge this gap by providing structured experiences that support concept formation and compensate for missed incidental learning, thereby laying a strong foundation for O&M skill development. Certain concepts, such as colour, are especially dependent on visual experience. Lowenfeld (1974) observed that colour perception is uniquely a function of the retina and cannot be fully accessed through other sensory modalities. As a result, individuals who are totally blind cannot have direct experiential knowledge of colour, which limits their conceptual understanding in this area.

Knoblock and Pasamanick (1974) cautioned that vision cannot be separated from other aspects of development, including posture, motor coordination, manual skills, intelligence, and personality. Vision serves as a primary source of stimulation and plays an integrative role in organizing information from other sensory systems during typical development. This interdependence helps explain why learners with visual impairments often receive specialized instruction in areas such as daily living skills and orientation and mobility to address developmental gaps associated with reduced visual input. Barraga (1983) emphasized the importance of maximizing the use of residual vision in individuals with visual impairments. Even minimal functional vision can have significant practical value, particularly when individuals are encouraged and supported to use it effectively. Providing opportunities for visual stimulation can enhance visual perception and contribute meaningfully to orientation and mobility performance.

Auditory Perception

Auditory perception is often considered one of the primary sensory channels used by individuals with blindness. The auditory system allows sound energy to reach the ears from multiple directions and across considerable distances, enabling the estimation of sound direction and distance (Hermelin & O'Connor, 1975). These auditory cues play a vital role in environmental awareness and spatial orientation. However, auditory perception also has limitations. Fraiberg (1975) noted that when a sound source is located directly in front of or behind a listener, accurate localization can be difficult without additional cues, such as those provided by head movement that make it possible to identify the objects that are responsible for making a particular sound.

The patterns of sound energy processed by the auditory system do not specify concretely the characteristics of objects that are readily appreciated by vision and touch, such as shape, size, texture and colour. When a person with visual impairment relies on sounds, unless they are attached to meaningful source, they would result into meaninglessness or nothingness. Despite these short fall, Barraga (1974) opined that the maintenance of human and environmental contact is more easily done and may provide more satisfying interactions in early and later life through the auditory sense.

Practical Training Strategies for Orientation and Mobility

1. Sensory Awareness and Discrimination Exercises

- a. Objective: Enhance the ability to recognize and differentiate environmental stimuli.

- b. **Texture Exploration:** Use various textured objects and surfaces (e.g., carpets, tiles, gravel) to train tactile discrimination.
- c. **Sound Identification:** Play different environmental sounds (e.g., traffic, footsteps, doorbells) and have learners identify and locate their sources.
- d. **Light and Residual Vision Use:** For those with residual sight, practice tracking moving objects and recognizing light sources under different lighting conditions.

2. Residual Vision Utilization

- a. **Objective:** Maximize the use of available vision.
- b. **Lighting Optimization:** Practice moving in environments with adequate lighting and teach techniques to adjust their gaze to maximize residual vision.
- c. **Sighted Guide Techniques:** Teach learners to use visual cues from a guide or environmental features for orientation.
- d. **Visual Scanning:** Encourage systematic scanning of surroundings to gather visual information effectively.

3. Auditory Orientation Skills

- a. **Objective:** Develop accurate sound localization and environmental awareness.
- b. **Sound Mapping:** Set up a controlled environment where learners identify the direction and distance of sound sources.
- c. **Environmental Sound Recognition:** Practice recognizing and interpreting common environmental sounds and their significance.
- d. **Active Listening Drills:** Encourage head movements and listening techniques to improve spatial hearing.

4. Tactile and Haptic Training

- a. **Objective:** Improve obstacle detection, environmental mapping, and object recognition.
- b. **Cane Skills Development:** Teach proper grip, sweeping techniques, and obstacle detection using the long cane.
- c. **Tactile Mapping:** Use tactile maps and models of local environments to familiarize learners with spatial layouts.
- d. **Object Recognition:** Practice identifying objects through touch (e.g., different door handles, furniture features).

5. Route and Environment Familiarization

- a. **Objective:** Build confidence in navigating familiar and unfamiliar routes.

- b. Route Repetition: Practice walking specific routes multiple times to develop spatial memory.
- c. Landmark Identification: Teach learners to identify and use environmental landmarks (e.g., benches, poles, signs) for orientation.
- d. Scenario-Based Drills: Simulate real-world situations such as crossing streets, navigating crowded areas, or using public transit.

6. Use of Mobility Aids and Tools

- a. Objective: Maximize safety and efficiency in navigation.
- b. Cane Techniques: Practice different cane techniques such as touch, tap, and sweep methods for obstacle detection.
- c. Electronic Aids: Introduce and train on GPS devices, auditory signals, or vibrotactile feedback tools.
- d. Environmental Adaptation: Teach how to adapt mobility strategies based on environmental conditions (e.g., rain, dim lighting).

7. Orientation in Complex Environments

- a. Objective: Prepare learners to handle unfamiliar or challenging settings.
- b. Crowded Area Navigation: Practice moving through busy streets, markets, or transit stations.
- c. Elevator and Stair Navigation: Focus on safe techniques for ascending/descending stairs and using elevators.
- d. Night and Low Light Navigation: Conduct exercises in low-light conditions to enhance perceptual skills.

8. Cognitive and Conceptual Development

- a. Objective: Foster understanding of spatial concepts and safety.
- b. Spatial Concept Drills: Practice understanding directions (left, right, forward, backward) and distances.
- c. Time and Sequence Training: Use timers and sequencing activities to develop temporal understanding.
- d. Problem-Solving Scenarios: Present challenges (e.g., detours, obstacles) to develop situational awareness and decision-making.

Additional Tips for Effective Training

- a. Gradual Progression: Start with simple tasks and gradually increase complexity.
- b. Real-World Practice: Use actual environments whenever possible to promote transfer of skills.

- c. Positive Reinforcement: Encourage learners with praise and feedback to build confidence.
- d. Personalized Approach: Tailor strategies to individual needs, residual vision levels, and environmental contexts.
- e. Safety First: Always prioritize safety, ensuring learners are supervised and equipped with appropriate aids.

Sample Lesson Plan: Basic Cane Skills and Environmental Orientation

Lesson Title: Introduction to Cane Use and Environmental Awareness

Duration: 60 minutes

Target Learners: Beginners with visual impairment (adults or older children)

Lesson Objectives:

- i. Learner will demonstrate proper grip and basic sweeping technique of the long cane.
- ii. Learner will identify and recognize at least three environmental landmarks using tactile methods.
- iii. Learner will practice safe walking along a familiar route with guidance.

Lesson Outline

Time	Activity	Detail/Procedure	Materials Needed
5 Minutes	Introduction and warm up	Briefly review safety rules and objectives. Engage in light stretching to prepare physically.	none
10 Minutes	Demonstration of Cane Grip and Technique	Instructor demonstrates proper grip, stance, and basic cane sweep. Emphasize relaxed posture and controlled movements.	Long cane
10 Minutes	Guided Practice: Cane Handling	Learner practices grip and sweeping motion, with instructor providing feedback. Focus on consistent rhythm and obstacle detection.	Long cane

10 Minutes	Tactile Exploration	Landmark	Learner explores tactile models or real environment features (e.g., textured mats, tactile maps) to identify landmarks such as pole, bench, or door.	Tactile models or environment features
10 Minutes	Environmental Localization	Sound	In a quiet outdoor or indoor setting, learner locates and identifies environmental sounds (e.g., footsteps, traffic, doorbell).	Environmental sounds (recordings or real)
10 Minutes	Walking Practice		Learner walks along a predefined familiar route (e.g., from classroom to exit or around a block), using cane and environmental cues. Instructor guides and provides feedback.	Safe walking route, instructor supervision
5 Minutes	Debrief and Reflection		Discuss what was learned, challenges faced, and feelings about the activity. Reinforce safety and confidence.	None

Lesson Notes and Tips:

- i. Safety First: Ensure the environment is free of hazards and that the learner is supervised at all times.
- ii. Positive Reinforcement: Praise correct techniques and efforts to boost confidence.
- iii. Adaptability: Modify activities based on learner's progress, environment, and specific needs.
- iv. Progression: Future lessons can introduce route planning, cross streets, and using other mobility aids.

Suggestions

To foster positive perceptions, service providers should adopt person-centered, respectful, and empowering approaches. Incorporating peer mentors and success stories can normalize O&M skills and reduce stigma (Lueck & Wacker, 2016). Increasing awareness about the benefits and dispelling myths about visual impairments are critical. Reducing logistical barriers by providing accessible, affordable, and geographically distributed services can improve perceptions. Training professionals in cultural competence and empathy enhances trust and satisfaction (Mckenzie, 2018). Policies should prioritize community-based, inclusive, and accessible O&M programs that respect individual preferences. Collaboration with disabled persons' organizations can improve outreach and perception.

Conclusion

Effective orientation and mobility training for persons with visual impairment hinges on the development of perceptual abilities, visual, auditory, and tactile. Each sense contributes uniquely to environmental understanding, hazard detection, and goal-oriented movement. Tailored training that enhances multisensory perception fosters greater independence, safety, and confidence in navigating the world. Recognizing the significance of perceptual development underscores the importance of comprehensive, individualized O & M programs that address sensory strengths and limitations, ultimately empowering individuals with visual impairments to lead active, autonomous lives.

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